

SINXRON TARJIMA JARAYONIDA SO‘Z DARAJASIDA ADEKVATLIKKA ERISHISH

Sarsenbayeva Mariya Agatovna

The teacher of the
Department of Foreign Languages and
Humanities at Cyber state university

msarsenbayeva@bk.ru;

+99890 353 34 37

Annotatsiya

Xususan, ushbu maqola quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi: Sinxron tarjima jarayonida leksik birliklarni tarjima qilish bilan bog'liq qiyinchiliklar; Sinxron tarjimada so'z darajasida ekvivalentlikka erishi; adekvatlikka erishishda qo'llanadigan tarjima usullari; Muqobilsiz frazeologik birliklar tarjimasi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sinxron tarjima, ekvivalentlik, So'zma-so'z tarjima, grammatik transformasiya.

Annotation

In particular, this article covers the following: difficulties associated with translating lexical units in the process of simultaneous translation; Achieving equivalence at the word level in simultaneous translation; Translation methods used to achieve adequacy; Translation of irreplaceable phraseological units.

Keywords: Simultaneous translation, equivalence, consecutive translation, grammatical transformation.

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются следующие вопросы: Трудности, связанные с переводом лексических единиц в процессе синхронного перевода; Достижение эквивалентности на уровне слов в синхронном переводе; Методы перевода, используемые для достижения адекватности; Перевод незаменимых фразеологических единиц.

Ключевые слова: Синхронный перевод, эквивалентность, дословный перевод, грамматическая трансформация.

Sinxron tarjima jarayonida leksik birliklarni tarjima qilish bilan bog‘liq qiyinchiliklar, ularning tarjima tilidagi adekvat variantini topish butun matnning ma'no-mazmuniga tasir qiladi. Sinxron tarjimada so‘zlarning adekvat tarjima qilishda asliyat va tarjima tillaridagi so‘zlarning o‘zaro bir-biriga leksik-semantik, uslubiy hamda kontekstual jihatidan mos kelganda so‘zlarning adekvatligiga ishonch xosil qilish mumkin.

Sinxron tarjimada so‘z darajasida ekvivalentlikka erishi uchun bir qator tarjima usullaridan mohirona foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq bo‘ladi.

Shu o‘rinda tarjima usullari borasida ayrim ma'lumotlarni taqdim etamiz. Tarjima usullari ilk bor Vinye va Darbelnye aniq metodologik maqsadga ko‘ra tasniflangan[3]. Ular “procédés techniques de la traduction” terminini qo‘llashgan. Bundan ko‘rinib turibdiki, ular tomonidan “tarjima jarayoni (translation procedure)” termini qo‘llangan. Olimlar transformasiyalarni uch sathda (leksik, morfologik va sintaktik, axborot) qo‘llanadigan jarayonlar deb tavsiflashgan. Ularning fikriga ko‘ra, transformasiyalar literal (so‘zma-so‘z) va oblique (ma'noviy) tarjima turlariga bo‘linadi. So‘zma-so‘z tarjima ikki til o‘rtasidagi aniq struktural, leksik va hatto morfologik ekvivalentlik mavjud bo‘lganda qo‘llanadi. Mualliflarning fikrlariga ko‘ra, bu faqatgina bir-biriga juda yaqin ikki til o‘rtasidagi tarjimada qo‘llanishi mumkin. Quyida Vinye va Darbelnye tomonidan taklif qilingan so‘zma-so‘z tarjima transformasiyalarini keltirib o‘tamiz: so‘z o‘zlashtirish, kalkalash, gaplarni birma-bir tarjima qilish. Ma'noviy tarjima transformasiyalariga quyidagilarni kiritgan: transpozitsiya, modulyatsiya, ekvivalentlik, moslashtirish, kompensatsiya, jamlash va qismlarga ajratish, kengaytirish va toraytirish, kuchaytirish va kamaytirish, eksplisit va implisit, umumiyashtirish va tavsiflash, inversiya.

E.Aznaurova rahbarligida bir guruh mualliflar leksik va grammantik transformasiyalar haqida ma'lumot berib o‘tgan. E.Aznaurova leksik transformasiyalarga quyidagilarni kiritgan: leksik almashinuvlar, antonimik tarjima,

kompensasiya, so‘z qo‘shish va so‘z tushirib qoldirish. Grammatik transformasiyalarga esa almashtirish, o‘zgarish, so‘z tushirib qoldirish va so‘z qo‘shishlarni kiritgan. O‘ziga xos realiyalarni tarjima qilish uchun transliteratsiya, ona tilidagi morfologik aloqadorlik yoki belgilar asosida biror predmetni ifodalash uchun yangi yoki qo‘shma so‘z yaratish va boshqa tilning realiyasiga yaqinroq so‘zdan foydalanish kabi tarjima transformasiyalarini kiritgan. Muqobilsiz frazeologik birliklar tarjimasida qo‘llanadigan tarjima transformasiyalariga so‘zma-so‘z tarjima, analog tarjima yo‘li bilan o‘girish va tasviriy tarjimalarni kiritgan[1].

L.Barxudarov tarjima jarayonida qo‘llanadigan transformasiyalarni to‘rt turga bo‘ladi: 1) joyni o‘zgartirish; 2) so‘z almashtirish; 3) so‘z qo‘shish; 4) so‘zni tushirib qoldirish[2].

Quyida adekvatlikka erishishda qo‘llanadigan tarjima usullari, ularning mazmun-mohiyati va ular orqali adekvat tarjima qilingan so‘zlarni keltirib o‘tamiz:

1. Ekvivalentlik – bunda xuddi shunday vaziyat uchun butunlay boshqa muqobil ibora ishlatiladi, ya'ni maqollar yoki idiomatik ifoda vositalari bularga misol bo‘la oladi. Quyidagi so‘zlar mazkur usul orqali ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinadi:

Commentator .n	A journalist who comments on current events a report by the political commentator in ‘The Times’ on unrest on the Government back benches	sharxlovchi
Commentary .n	1. a set of notes which comment on the main points of a document 2. A book which comments on the law	1.Sharh, izoh 2.Qonun sharhi
Commander .n	The officer in charge of a police district in London. Abbr Cmd., Cmdr, com., Com., Comdr	Boshliq, raxbar

Communiqué .n	an official announcement In a communiqué from the Presidential Palace, the government announced that the President would be going on a world tour	Bayonnoma, bayonot
Compatriot . n	a person from the same country	Vatandosh
Compensatory .n	providing somebody or a group with payment to help remove the pain or offence cause by some wrong action done to them	Zararni qoplash
Confederate .adj	joined in common purpose	Bir maqsadda birlashgan
Conquer .v	to defeat by force: The victorious army is engaged in establishing the rule of law in the areas which it has conquered.	Bosib olmoq
Collegiate .adj	sharing responsibilities as a group collegiate decisions taken by a group of people collectively	hamkasb
Colonial .adj	referring to countries ruled over or settled by other countries Granting of independence ended a period of a hundred years of colonial rule. The colonial government was overthrown by a coup led by the local police force	mustamlakachi
Colonialist. n	believing in colonialism _____ noun a person who believes in colonialism	mustamlakachi
Colonisation .n	the act of making a country into a colony	mustamlakachi lik

Colonise .(verb)	to take possession of an area or country and rule it as a colony The government was accused of trying to colonise the Antarctic Region	mustamlakaga aylantirmoq
Colonist . n	a person who goes or is sent to another country or region to settle in a colony	Mustamlakachi
Command. (noun) (verb)	1. an order 2. leadership He has or is in command of the armed forces 3 .to order someone to do something 4. to command support to be good enough to have the support of voters The measure commands widespread support in the House.	1. buyruq, farmon 2. boshqaruv, qo‘l ostida bo‘lish 3. buyruq bermoq 4. boshqarmoq
Commander .n	The officer in charge of a police district in London. Abbr Cmd., Cmdr, com., Com., Comdr	boshliq, raxbar
Commence .vb	to begin In the House of Commons, the business of the day commences with prayers. The proceedings commenced with the swearing-in of witnesses	boshlamoq
Commerce (noun)	noun business activities or the buying and selling of goods and services. Chamber of Commerce	Tijorat, savdo-sotiq
Commercial .adj	adjective 1. referring to business 2. intended to make money	1.savdo-sotiqqa oid

		2.foydaga qaratilgan
Commit (Verb)	to send a bill to a parliamentary committee to be reviewed He was committed for trial at the Crown Court.	Qonun loyihasini ko‘rib chiqish uchun parlament qo‘mitasiga yuborish
Committed .adj	1. holding strong political views : : She isa committed socialist. 2. already promised to be used in a specific way : Half next year’s budget is already committed. The government’s subsidy has been committed to repairs to the Town Hall. 3. obliged to act in a particular way : The council is committed to a policy of increasing services and reducing property taxes.	1.fidokor 2.sarflangan 3. muayyan tarzda harakat qiladigan
Committee .n	1. an official group of people who organise or plan for a larger group to be a member of a committee or to sit on a committee He was elected to the Finance Committee.	1. Qo‘mita
Common .adj	referring to or belonging to several different people or to everyone the common good the interest of all members of society the government is working for the common good	1. O‘xshash umumiy

	of the people common ownership ownership of a company or a property by a group of people who each own a part	
Commonalty .n	ordinary people considered as a political class, as compared with the upper classes	Oddiy xalq

2.Funksional ekvivalentlik – Bunda tarjima tili leksikasida so‘z aslyat tili leksikasidagi bir xil vazifani bajaruvchi matn uslubiga mos keladigan so‘z bilan almashtiriladi. Quyidagi so‘zlar mazkur usul orqali ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinadi:

immigrant / noun/	a person who moves into a country to live permanently	muhojir
immigrate / verb/	to move into a country to live permanently	ko‘chirib ketish
vacuum cleaner	a <u>machine</u> that <u>cleans floors</u> and other <u>surfaces</u> by <u>sucking up dust</u> and <u>dirt</u>	chang yutgich
freezer	a <u>container</u> , <u>operated</u> by <u>electricity</u> , that <u>stores food</u> at a very <u>cold temperature</u> so that it <u>becomes solid</u> and can be <u>kept safely</u> for a <u>long time</u> :	muzlatgich
mixer	a <u>machine</u> that <u>mixes substances</u> :	aralashtirgich
printer	a <u>machine</u> that is <u>connected</u> to a <u>computer</u> and <u>prints</u> onto <u>paper</u> using <u>ink</u> :	chop ettirgich

3.Tasviriy ekvivalentlik – usulda leksik birlikni bildiruvchi so‘zning ma'nosi bir necha so‘zlarda tushuntiriladi.

Commencement order (noun)	an order that brings an Act or part of an act into effect after the Royal Assent has been given	qirollik roziligi berilgandan keyin qonun yoki uning bir qismini kuchga kirituvchi buyruq
Commit (Verb)	to send a bill to a parliamentary committee to be reviewed He was committed for trial at the Crown Court.	Qonun loyihasini ko'rib chiqish uchun parlament qo'mitasiga yuborish.
Commitment (noun)	promise or agreement to do something We have honoured the commitments made in our manifesto.	bajarilishi kerak bo'lgan vazifa
Committee Stage	noun one of the stages in the discussion of a Bill, where each clause is examined in detail The Bill is at Committee Stage and will not become law for several months	Parlament uyidagi to'lov hisobi ikkinchi va uchinchi o'qish o'rtasidagi bosqich.
Common market	an economic association of countries with the aim of removing or reducing trade barriers	Past bojxona to'lovlariga kelishib olishgan davlatlar

Demak, sinxron tarjimada so'zlarni adekvat tarjima qilishda ularning avvalo denotativ ma'nolariga e'tibor qaratish maqsadga muvofiq bo'lib, bir shaklga ega leksik birliklarni tarjima qilishda ekvivalentlik, ekvivalentlikning ko'rinishlari eslatmalar kabi tarjima usullaridan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi.

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